

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: A CHALLENGE TO INDIA

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Abstract

Sustainable development in this environment therefore, calls for cooperation of all countries both industrialized and developing. That cooperation must be based on the foundation of the right to development and the need for an equitable distribution of burden. The need for equity is starkly reflected in the fact that the emissions per capita in industrialized countries are ten to twelve times those of developing countries. The total emissions in the world must decline. We must find a way of solving this problem in a way that does not deprive developing countries of their right to develop. Economic growth, social development and environment protection are the three pillars of Sustainable development. Sustainability has different meanings for different contexts. For example, while developed countries are grappling with lifestyle sustainability, the developing countries are tackling issues of livelihood sustainability. As a developing country in the frontlines of climate vulnerability, India has a vital stake in the evolution of a successful, rule-based, equitable and multilateral response to issues relating to climate change. From time to time International communities setup the sustainable goals for countries across the world. In this paper, researcher tries to describe the sustainable development. India's progress towards United Nations' Millennium Development Goals. In the end paper also talk about India initiated towards sustainable development.

Keywords: *Sustainable Development, MDGs, SDGs*

Sustainable Development

According to the report 'Our common future' by Ms. Harlem Brundtland, sustainable development is defined as development that satisfies the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to satisfy theirs. This report, published in 1987

by the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development, insists on the need to protect the diversity of genes, species, and all terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems in nature. This is possible in particular via measures to protect the quality of the environment, and by the restoration, development, and maintenance of habitats that are essential to species. This implies the sustainable management of the use of the animal and plant populations being exploited. In other words, it is the rational management of human, natural, and economic resources that aims to satisfy the essential needs of humanity in the very long term.

India makes up 2.4 percent of the world's land, while supporting 16 percent of the world's population. The compounding result is a severely unsustainable use of natural resources for several generations. Currently, India is experiencing rapid and widespread environmental degradation at alarming rates. Tremendous pressure is placed upon the country's land and natural resources to support the massive overpopulation.

Mismanagement and overuse of India's once abundant forests has resulted in desertification, contamination, and soil depletion throughout the sub-continent. This has serious repercussions for the livelihoods of hundreds of millions of Indians that live off the land. In Rajasthan alone, it is approximated that nearly five million tribal people (as of 2004) rely on the collection of forest produce as their only source of income or nourishment. Without continual access to forest products such as fruit, honey, or firewood these communities experience debilitating hunger and are reduced to extreme poverty.

Sustainable Development in India

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must decline. We must find a way of solving this problem in a way that does not deprive developing countries of their right to develop.

Economic growth, social development and environment protection are the three pillars of Sustainable development. Sustainability has different meanings for different contexts. For example, while developed countries are grappling with lifestyle sustainability, the developing countries are tackling issues of livelihood sustainability.

As a developing country in the frontlines of climate vulnerability, India has a vital stake in the evolution of a successful, rule-based, equitable and multilateral response to issues relating to climate change. The principles of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change provide the basis for creating a workable framework along these lines.

India's Progress towards Sustainable Development:

There is a strong sense of progress made at community level, where it matters. India has made remarkable gains so far in sustainable development, as measured, for example, in three summary 'outcome' indicators.

- i. Life Expectancy, India has achieved a decade's gain, which is a broad indicator of economic well-being with social justice.
- ii. Forest Cover, there has also been a rise in forest cover despite the pressures on land use, which is a measure of environmental sustainability. Satellite data confirms that not only has India been able to control deforestation, but its forest cover has also been increasing between the 1990s and 2011. India is one of the few developing countries where forest cover has increased over the last 20 years and continues to increase, although a slight dip is reported in the latest data for 2011.
- iii. Literacy a third summary indicator is gains in literacy among younger women, an indicator of future generations' well-being.

- iv. On all three counts, India has outpaced the ‘deltas’ on global averages, although it could have done even better.
- v. The Constitution of India and relevant amendments that have been incorporated over the years, reinforce the policy and legal basis of sustainable development in India. The pillars of sustainable development are embedded in the fundamental rights guaranteed by the Constitution, which lay down the framework for social justice in India.
- vi. Article 21 conferring the Right to Life has been assigned the broadest interpretations by the judiciary to encompass the right to a clean environment, right to livelihood, right to live with dignity, and a number of other associated rights.
- vii. The National Environment Policy 2006-has attempted to mainstream environmental concerns in all developmental activities. The Government of India, through its various policies, has been factoring ecological concerns into the development process so that economic development can be achieved without permanently damaging the environment. The challenges ahead are, nevertheless, large.

India Progress on Millennium Development Goals

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) have helped in bringing out a much needed focus and pressure on basic development issues, which in turn led the governments at national and regional levels to do better planning and implement more intensive policies and programmes. The MDGs originated from the Millennium Declaration adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations in September 2000. The MDGs consists of eight goals, and these eight goals address myriad development issues. The eight (8) Goals are

Goal 1: Eradicate Extreme Poverty and Hunger

Goal 2: Achieve Universal Primary Education

Goal 3: Promote Gender Equality and Empower Women

Goal 4: Reduce Child Mortality

Goal 5: Improve Maternal Health

Goal 6: Combat HIV/AIDS, Malaria and TB

Goal 7: Ensure Environmental Sustainability

Goal 8: Develop Global Partnership for Development

Figure 1: India's Progress on Millennium Development Goals

Source: India and the MDGs, towards a sustainable future for all, United Nation

The Real Challenges to Sustainable Development

With the expiry of the MDGs which guided global development till 2015, the international community is now negotiating Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for the period 2016-2030.

The main challenges to sustainable development which are global in character include poverty and exclusion, unemployment, climate change, conflict and humanitarian aid, building peaceful and inclusive societies, building strong institutions of governance, and supporting the rule of law.

Figure 2: Sustainable Development Goals

Source: <http://www.counterview.org>

- Ending of poverty in all its forms everywhere by 2030 and eradicating extreme poverty for all everywhere, now measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day
- Ending hunger, achieving food security and improved nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture by 2030
- Ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting life-long learning opportunities for all by 2030
- Ensuring availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all by 2030
- Ensuring access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all by 2030

- Promoting sustained, inclusive and economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all
- Sustaining per capita economic growth in accordance with national circumstances and in particular, at least 7 percent per annum GDP growth in the least-developed countries
- Building resilient infrastructure and promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialisation
- Encouraging innovation by developing quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure, including regional and trans-border infrastructure, to support economic development and human well-being
- Reducing inequality within and among countries by 2030
- Making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable by 2030
- Ensuring sustainable consumption and production patterns
- Taking urgent action to stop and mitigate climate change and its impacts through resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries
- Conserving and sustainably using the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development by 2025
- Protecting, restoring and promoting sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems; sustainably managing forests, combating desertification, and halting and reversing land degradation and biodiversity loss by 2020.
- Providing access to justice for all and promote effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels

There are several lines of argument that have arisen from the above. Charles Gore, a member of the UN Millennium Project's UN Experts Group, has observed that the translation of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) to SDGs has led to the reduction of these broader goals into national aims, which could in fact harm the achievements of the SDGs that involve policy discussions, issues of universality, the gains of a partnership approach, the principle of common and differentiated responsibility and mechanisms of accountability

India Initiated to Sustainable Development

According to the latest Economic Survey, India has announced a domestic goal of reducing the emission intensity of its GDP by 20-25 per cent (at the 2005 levels) by 2020. The following are the key enablers of this vision as per the latest economic survey of the government:

- 1. National Solar Mission:** The program Seeks to deploy 20,000 MW of solar electricity capacity in the country by 2020. The first phase (2010-12) is currently underway during which 1,000 MW is planned to be installed, and about Rs. 4,337 crore will be spent on it.
- 2. National Mission for Enhanced Energy Efficiency:** This mission aims to create new institutional mechanisms to enable the development and Energy Efficiency strengthening of energy efficiency markets. Various programmes initiated under it include the PAT mechanism to promote efficiency in large industries, and the Super-Efficient Equipment Programme (SEEP) to accelerate the introduction of deployment of super- efficient appliances.
- 3. National Mission on Sustainable Habitat:** It has been envisioned to promote the introduction of sustainable transport, energy-efficient buildings, sustainable Habitat and sustainable waste management in cities. About Rs. 1,000 crore would be needed to realise these goals.
- 4. National Water Mission:** This mission is to promote the integrated management of water resources and increase water use efficiency by 20 per cent, and a whopping Rs. 89,101 crore will be spent on it.
- 5. National Mission for Sustaining the Himalayan Eco-system:** The Himalayas, as grand they are, are also a relatively new ecosystem and too fragile at that. This program, therefore, establishes an observational and monitoring network for Himalayan glaciers, and looks forward to promote community- based management of ecosystems. More than Rs. 1100 crore would be spent on these goals. National Mission for Green India: This program would result in afforestation of an additional 10 million hectare of forest lands, wastelands and community lands, over the next 10 years, with a cost of Rs. 46,000.
- 6. National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture:**The focus of this mission is on enhancing productivity and resilience of agriculture, in order to reduce vulnerability to

extremes of weather, long dry spells, flooding, and variable moisture availability. It will invite a total investment of Rs. 108,000 crore.

- 7. National Mission on Strategic Knowledge for Climate Change:** This program would aim to identify challenges arising from climate change. It will also look into the possibility of diffusion of knowledge in the areas of health, demography, migration and livelihood of coastal communities.

A total of Rs. 1050 crore will be spent on it. Clearly, India's doing all she can do in her capacity to prevent a dark future of our planet. India's leadership show at Durban and her commitment to sustainability is something every Indian should be proud of.

Conclusion

Sustainable development is a vision and a way of thinking and acting so that we can secure the resources and environment for our future generation. It will not be brought about by policies only, it must be taken up by society at large as a principle guiding the many choices each citizen makes every day, as well as the big political and economic decisions that affect many. It is clear that environmental degradation tends to impose the largest costs on those generations that are yet to be born. Future generations are disadvantaged with regards to present generations because they can inherit an impoverished quality of life, share a condition of structural weakness in having no voice and representation among the present generation and so their interests are often neglected in present decisions and planning while it is very much needful that we think about our generation. We can only improve sustainable development when it will put an emphasis on involving citizens and stakeholders. Ultimately, the vision will become reality only if everybody contributes to a world where economic freedom, social justice and environmental protection go hand in hand, making our own and future generations better off than now.

REFERENCES

Nagesh, K. (2015). *India and the MDGs Towards A Sustainable future for all*. United Nation India.

RUSKO, M., & PROCHÁZKOVÁ, D. (2011). Solution to the problems of the sustainable development management. *FACULTY OF MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY IN TRNAVA, SLOVAK UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY IN BRATISLAVA* , 77-84.

Sengupta, A., & Sonwani, D. (2012). Sustainable Development in India with Reference to Agricultural Sector. *International Journal of Emerging Research in Management & Technology* , 24-29.

www.counterview.org

www.meritnation.com

www.planningcommission.nic.in

www.sustainabledevelopment.un.org